

On Triethylene Trisulphide and 1:4-Dithian

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Triethylene trisulphide and its derivatives have already been described by one of us (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1920, 117, 1090; *ibid.*, 1922, 121, 1279). Bennet and Berry (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 127, 910) have recently prepared this cyclic polysulphide and conclude that the so-called trisulphide is in reality 1:4-dithian.

In view of this divergence in views we have recently re-investigated the subject and we find that the compounds prepared by our method as also by V. Meyer's method are identical in properties. A molecular weight determination in benzene solution gave the value 119.5, that required by the formula $(C_2H_4)_3S_2$ being 120. Bennet and Berry determined the molecular weight in nitrobenzene solution.

There are, however, substantial grounds for adhering to the formula previously proposed. It has been already hinted at that in certain cases this complex sulphide parts with the group C_2H_4S and is converted into the simpler modification (*loc. cit.*, 1280), in other words, the one form can easily pass into the other. Moreover, the formation of the two distinct platinum derivatives $(C_2H_4)_3S_2PtCl_3$ and $(C_2H_4)_3S_3PtCl_4$ cannot be accounted for except on the assumption that in certain cases polymerisation does take place,¹ thus:

¹ The substance depolymerises in the gaseous state as well as in dilute solution; the vapour density of the substance was measured by Hoffmann's method, and it conformed approximately to the formula $(C_2H_4)_2S_2$ (cf. $2O_2 \rightleftharpoons 3O_3$).

It has lately been found that when the dithian is treated with an aqueous instead of an alcoholic solution of chloroplatinic acid, the compound of the formula $(\text{C}_2\text{H}_4)_3\text{S}_2\text{PtCl}_3$ is *invariably* obtained. Its formation justifies the use of the formula $(\text{C}_2\text{H}_4)_3\text{S}_3$ for the sulphide in question; the dropping off of an atom of sulphur has already been noticed when a sulphide is loaded with a heavy molecule like platinum chloride (*loc. cit.*, 1279; *cf.* also Mann and Pope, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, 123, 1179). Dithian $(\text{C}_2\text{H}_4)_2\text{S}_2$ cannot be expected to yield a compound containing three ethylene radicles—in fact, these platinum compounds are crucial instances in support of our view.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Resublimed dithian (m. p. 113°) was heated with an aqueous solution of platinum chloride and continuously 'teased' with a rod. A yellow crystalline compound was formed. It was drained on filter paper, washed with water, dried and then washed with boiling benzene to remove traces of dithian that might be present. The preparation was repeated several times. (Found: Pt = 43.68, 43.52, 43.26, 43.44; Cl = 24.25; S = 14.58; C = 15.33; H = 2.23. $(\text{C}_2\text{H}_4)_3\text{S}_2\text{PtCl}_3$ requires Pt = 43.63; Cl = 23.59; S = 14.17; C = 15.94; H = 2.66 per cent.)

As compounds of this type have been known to contain alcohol or ether of crystallisation (this *Journal*, 1924, 1, 70; foot-note), care was taken not to use alcohol or ether in the preparation, because discrimination between $(\text{C}_2\text{H}_4)_3\text{S}_2\text{PtCl}_3$ and $(\text{C}_2\text{H}_4)_2\text{S}_2\text{PtCl}_3$, EtOH by analysis is difficult.